

ASSESSMENT OF DURABILITY MODELS FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Seth S. Kessler¹, Jeremy R. Gregory¹, Dennis A. Burianek² and S. Mark Spearing¹

¹*Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA 02139*
²*Lincoln Laboratory, Lexington, MA 02420*

SUMMARY

The ability to model durability related damage and failure mechanisms is discussed. Prior work on the elevated temperature fatigue of titanium-graphite hybrid laminates is reviewed and used to illustrate the guiding principles for constructing a framework for durability modeling. The important role of multiple interacting damage modes is highlighted and the possibility of developing ad hoc mechanism-based models to describe such damage states is discussed. These principles are applied to the selection of simple mechanistic models to aid the designer in dealing with durability in the context of the Accelerated Insertion of Materials — Composites (AIM-C) program. Simple models for durability-relevant material behavior, such as fatigue crack growth, moisture absorption, multiple matrix cracking, hygrothermal degradation of elastic properties and failure related material response are available but have generally not been widely implemented. The provision of such models to the durability engineer should allow for an improvement in the overall approach to durability assessment. In particular the provision of such models should facilitate the development of ad hoc models for interacting damage, degradation and failure modes, which are a key to a successful durability prediction. This approach requires that experienced engineers are guiding the process, and has the modest aim of reducing, rather than eliminating, the reliance on testing, and thereby accelerating the overall durability assessment process.

KEY TERMS: Durability, Hybrid Laminate, Fatigue, Moisture, Temperature, Polymer Matrix Composite

INTRODUCTION

The insertion of new materials, notably composites, has proven to be a time-consuming and expensive activity that has proved to be a significant barrier to their use. The time to develop a new material technology and qualify it for use in an aerospace system is often far longer than the time required to develop the rest of the system. Designing for durability can be an important reason for the long time required to introduce a new material. The research described herein discusses a durability component of the larger overall DARPA sponsored Accelerated Insertion of Materials Composites (AIM-C) effort. The objective of AIM-C is to demonstrate concepts, approaches and tools that can accelerate the insertion of new materials into Department of Defense products. The AIM-C concept is to utilize analytical techniques and experimentation together in an efficient manner in order to develop a designer knowledge base from the outset, rather than the more traditional approach of sequential, unlinked research and development, sometimes locally optimized without a production readiness transition path.

It is important to understand the key concern regarding durability before embarking on a model development/assessment exercise. The working definition of durability that is being employed in AIM-C is as follows: *Durability is primarily an economic issue affecting the inspection intervals, repair costs, and service life of a structure. The key durability metric is the time it takes for flaws to begin to initiate in nominal structure.*

Underlying this definition is the concept that flight structures will be regularly inspected and if flaws (or damage due to the chemical or thermal environment) are detected then a repair or replacement of the part will be carried out - which will contribute to the overall operating cost of the system. In designing for durability it is generally not possible to consider every loading and environmental situation and their interactions. Thus the existing approach to designing for durability is to entrust the task to experienced personnel who draw on their experience to anticipate the likely damage/failure mechanisms and to implement test programs to probe them and to refine the design according to the test results. The two keys are (1) to avoid unanticipated durability problems and (2) to minimize the scale of the testing effort required to achieve (1). This process is generally quite effective, however it is ripe for improvement by introducing modeling and simulation to augment the generally heuristic approach.

One of the core problems associated with implementing a model-based strategy to address the issue of durability is that the failure of composite structures is generally controlled by multiple interacting damage modes. This occurs to some extent in dealing with the durability of metallic structures, where failure mechanisms such as fatigue and corrosion can interact or multi-site fatigue damage can accumulate to cause ultimate failure. However, for the most part durability can be adequately addressed by considering single failure mechanisms in isolation and the concern is predominantly focused on fatigue damage. For composite structures the situation is more complicated, nonetheless it is possible to develop models that provide some predictive capability albeit without the universal applicability that fracture mechanics has demonstrated in guiding design against fatigue. Recent work on Titanium/Graphite (TiGr) hybrid laminates provides a useful illustrative example, both of the difficulties of multiple damage and the sort of progress that can be made by the sensible implementation of modeling. Given that TiGr is a candidate material for high temperature aerospace applications it is important to understand the mechanisms that control its durability under conditions of elevated temperature, cyclic loading. A complete description of the research on TiGr is included in references [1-5]. The relevant sections are reproduced here for the purposes of illustration.

AN EXAMPLE OF INTERACTING DAMAGE MECHANISMS

The initial TiGr testing consisted of performing tension-compression cyclic loading of open hole specimens at an R-ratio of -0.2. S-N data such as that shown in **Figure 1** was obtained. Functional failures occurred due to the specimen jamming in the anti-buckling guide, so a local stiffness reduction of 50% was adopted as an effective failure criterion, reflecting the observation that failure occurred due to a local stiffness reduction, resulting in buckling. Data was obtained by monitoring an extensometer mounted across the center of the hole on the specimen. Typical damage is shown in **Figure 2**. Fatigue cracks occurred in the surface Titanium plies, initiating at the whole edge and then propagating to the specimen edge. Removal of the facesheets and use of a penetrant clearly shows a triangular delamination accompanying the face sheet cracks. Once the cracks reach the edge of the specimen the delamination propagates rapidly towards the grips. It is this process that contributes to the majority of the stiffness reduction and to the failure of the specimens in compression. **Figure 3** shows stiffness reduction vs. cycles for specimens cycled at different load levels. The initial 5% stiffness reduction is due to the facesheet cracking and accompanying delamination and the subsequent decrease in stiffness is due to delamination propagation. **Figure 4** shows the effect of temperature on the rate of stiffness reduction.

In order to understand the effects of temperature on delamination growth additional tests were performed on specimens with seams in the titanium facesheets. Delaminations preferentially initiate at these locations, and their stable growth can be monitored. **Figure 5** shows delamination growth rate data at room temperature and 177°C. The rates at the higher temperature are nearly an order of magnitude faster than at room temperature. Literature data indicates that to about 300°C temperature has little effect on fatigue crack growth rates of titanium alloys.

A model was developed for the growth of combined face sheet cracking and delamination. A 3-D finite element model was constructed of the facesheet crack and accompanying triangular delamination. This allowed the crack tip stress intensity factor to be calculated and the stiffness reduction due to the coupled damage mechanisms. Using the literature data for the dependence of the crack growth rate on stress intensity factor predictions can be made for the crack growth rate. **Figure 6** shows such predictions for loading at three different stress levels. A very good prediction of data is obtained without any "tuning" to the data. Furthermore the relatively weak effect of temperature on the face-sheet crack growth rate is correctly described by this modeling approach, as shown in **Figure 7**. For the subsequent stiffness reduction due to delamination propagation away from the face sheet cracks, laminated plate theory was used to predict the reduction in stiffness with sequential separation of the face sheets. The rate of delamination growth was obtained by fitting a "Paris Law" to data such as that shown in **Figure 5**. This approach results in a reasonable ability to predict the stiffness reduction as a function of loading and temperature, as illustrated by **Figure 8**. The models can also be used to re-create the S-N curve presented in **Figure 1**; this is shown in **Figure 9**. Note, due to the accumulation of modeling errors, the combined models need to be "tuned" using a scaling factor to fit the data, nevertheless the linked models do correctly describe the trends observed experimentally and allow engineers to understand better the factors that combine to govern the durability of this particular material system.

Two key lessons emerge from this study. First, even at the coupon level, several mechanisms combine to control the life of test specimens. S-N data such as that shown in **Figure 1** is the result of three distinct damage/failure mechanisms: delamination, face sheet cracking and local buckling. Furthermore, there are two distinct regimes of failure, the first in which the facesheet cracks and associated delamination initiate and grow from the hole edge to the specimen edge and the second in which the delamination grows along the length of the specimen. These regimes and the individual failure/damage mechanisms are affected in quite distinct ways by variables such as temperature, load level and specimen size. Therefore prediction of a durability-related response, such as an S-N curve, is not a straightforward process. The second lesson is that despite the complexity of the durability response, it is nonetheless possible to make useful predictions using relatively simple modeling approaches. These models might be termed "ad hoc" models insofar as they are not globally applicable, but are constructed based on experimental observations of damage modes. Once the damage modes are identified it is then possible to create models which allow for a significant reduction in the number of tests required and also permit an assessment of the relative severity of different load/environmental cases and their interactions. Even then, when the models are linked together errors in the individual models accumulate, necessitating the use of tuning factors to compensate.

EXTENSION OF THE APPROACH FOR AIM-C

Following the lessons learnt in the study of TiGr, and also earlier work on the fatigue of graphite/epoxy laminates [6,7] it is possible to generalize the approach to provide a design engineer with a set of tools that will facilitate the construction of ad hoc models relevant to the prediction of durability. These models can be used independently or may be linked together, where error accumulation does not become an overwhelming factor. The ultimate decisions regarding design, testing and even the decision to link the models or use them in isolation must still be taken by experienced engineers, as is the case in the current process, but they will permit a more quantitative basis for the decisions. For this process to be effective the models to be implemented must be properly validated, both against experimental data and against reasonable physical limits.

The particular durability components considered under this program include fatigue delamination initiation and growth, moisture absorption, thermal effects, and distributed microcracking:

Fatigue Crack Growth: It is relatively straightforward to calculate stress intensity factors for delaminations and fatigue cracks using procedures similar to those outlined above and documented in references [3] and [6]. In addition, automated meshing codes are becoming available that allow for the insertion of cracks at interfaces and the application of appropriate crack growth laws. It is also possible to couple the effects of moisture and temperature in terms of their effect on crack growth rate, using methods such as those applied in reference [2]. Furthermore attempts are being made to obtain a greater physical basis for the effects of moisture and temperature on the delamination fracture response [8].

Moisture Absorption: The modeling of moisture diffusion in laminates is relatively well established, and one dimensional linear Fickian diffusion models have been shown to work well in describing the time to saturate and the weight gain of structures due to moisture uptake [9-11]. In order to contribute to durability predictions it is necessary to allow for more local predictions of the moisture state, and to allow for the coupling to models for fatigue, and to variations in residual stress. **Figure 10** shows typical ply-by-ply predictions of moisture uptake in a thick composite laminate. Such information can be utilized to guide the development of representative combined loading and hygrothermal cycles.

Hygro-thermal Effects: There are two important consequences of local changes in the hygrothermal state of plies within a laminate [13, 14]. The first is the alteration of residual stress states, which are often important contributors to other damage processes, notably off-axis ply cracking. The second effect is in the alteration of the material response itself, by processes such as physical aging, matrix plasticization and creep.

Distributed Microcracking: There has been extensive modeling for the failure process of distributed microcracking(off-axis ply cracking) as it is an important failure mode observed in cyclic hygrothermal loading. Fracture mechanics approaches have been used successfully to predict the evolution of crack density with cyclic loading or temperature cycling [14, 15]. **Figures 11** and **12** show typical predictions of crack density evolution with a ramped thermal load or mechanical load cycling.

Degraded Material Properties: Given a damage or degradation state it is important to be able to predict the resulting stiffness of the structure, so as to be able to predict load redistribution and to anticipate the possibility of local or global buckling. Several models are available to account for these effects [16, 17] and are readily implemented in existing laminate plate theory codes, which in turn can be readily embedded in structural finite element codes.

The modeling approaches listed here have been validated against experimental data and are amenable to implementation as simple computer codes. These codes can be made available to durability engineers either in the form of stand alone modules, or as linked packages. Web-based software is being explored as a means to make the modules readily accessible and to facilitate linking them together when it makes sense to do so.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A model-augmented approach to durability prediction is advocated. Simple models for durability-relevant material behavior are readily available but have generally not been widely implemented. The provision of such models to the durability engineer should allow for an improvement in the overall approach to durability assessment. In particular the provision of such models should facilitate the development of ad hoc models for interacting damage, degradation and failure modes, which are a key to a successful durability prediction. This approach requires that experienced engineers are guiding the process, and has the modest aim of reducing, rather than eliminating, the reliance on testing, and thereby accelerating the overall durability assessment process.

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Figure 4. Stiffness reduction vs. cycles for two temperatures, 177°C and room temperature (23°C).

Figure 5. Delamination growth rate vs. applied strain energy release rate at two temperatures, 177°C and 23°C.

Figure 6. Predictions of fatigue face-sheet crack growth rate vs applied stress intensity factor for TiGr laminates cycled at three stress levels.

Figure 7. Predictions of fatigue face-sheet crack growth rate vs applied stress intensity factor for TiGr laminates cycled at two temperatures.

Figure 8. Predictions of stiffness reduction vs cycles for combined crack and delamination growth

Figure 9. Predictions of S-N behavior based on a local 50% stiffness drop.

Figure 10. Predictions of moisture uptake in a 100 ply laminate, the 50th ply is the external ply

Figure 11. Crack density vs temperature

Figure 12. Crack density vs cycles